

PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES FOR DEVELOPING ICT COMPETENCE IN ECONOMICS EDUCATION: A QUASI EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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Annotation. This research aims to explore the pedagogical opportunities for developing Information and Communication Technology (ICT) competence in future economists. The primary objective of the study is to identify effective pedagogical approaches for shaping ICT competence in economics students. The research utilizes a quasi-experimental method, analyzing the integration of interactive learning tools and digital education platforms. The findings indicate that the integration of ICT tools into the educational process enhances students' abilities to search, analyze, and apply information in practice. Incorporating innovative pedagogical approaches into curricula increases student motivation and strengthens their ICT skills. In conclusion, the development of ICT competence in economics education not only deepens students' knowledge but also prepares them for practical application, ultimately fostering the production of competitive professionals for the labor market.

Key words: Information and Communication Technologies, competence, pedagogical approaches, educational process, innovative technologies, digital education.

Introduction. The global integration of the modern economy calls for skilled professionals in Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). ICT plays a vital role in processing information, analyzing economic processes, decision-making, and managing databases. Equipping future economists with skills to gather, analyze, and present information holds significant economic and social importance. Unfortunately, practical programs aimed at developing ICT competence for students in economics are still lacking in many higher education institutions.

Modern technologies increase the possibilities for quick information

processing and analysis in economics and support efficient decision-making. ICT tools enhance essential skills for economic analysis, forecasting, and modeling. Furthermore, developing ICT competence facilitates efficient organization of economic analysis and decision-making processes. The advancement of scientific and technological progress has improved the efficiency of ICT tools, thereby increasing the demand for highly qualified specialists in economic analysis and decision-making. Developing ICT competence for economics students in higher education strengthens their economic knowledge and enhances analytical skills.

The main goal of the research is to develop effective pedagogical approaches for fostering ICT competence in economics students and to study their practical effectiveness. The study seeks to answer the following questions:

What pedagogical strategies can effectively develop ICT competence for economics students?

How do interactive and digital educational tools contribute to the enhancement of students' ICT competence?

To what extent does ICT competence development impact economic analysis and decision-making skills?

Literature Review and Methods. In recent years, the development of ICT competence has become an important topic in education. Mishra and Koehler's (2016) TPACK model emphasizes the integration of technology, pedagogy, and educational content to actively engage students in the learning process.[1] John and Smith (2018) highlight the need for ICT integration in economics education to equip students with skills in information searching and analysis.[2] Brown et al. (2019) emphasize the role of ICT tools in economic data analysis, as well as the use of statistical programs and databases.[3] Wu and Li (2020) underscore the role of economic modeling programs in developing ICT competence.[4] Hoffman and Weiss (2021) stress the improvement of economic analysis skills through interactive platforms.[5] Alqahtani and Bukhari (2022) demonstrate that digital technology enhances motivation and data processing skills in education.[6] Shirk (2019) supports the integration of ICT tools in economics curricula to prepare students for practical economic processes.[7] Zhao and Xu (2023) study the effectiveness of

projects and assignments in practicing ICT skills.[8] Since 2020, research on the broad integration of digital technologies into curricula has intensified. Wood and Parker (2022) recommend assignments based on real data to strengthen economic concepts.[9] Harper and Turner (2024) explore the role of economic modeling programs in increasing student interest and ICT skills.[10]

This article employs a quasi-experimental approach to analyze and evaluate pedagogical processes that shape ICT competence in economics students. The study examined differences between experimental and control groups and assessed the effectiveness of digital tools in teaching. The students were divided into two groups: an experimental group that received training through innovative pedagogical approaches, including interactive digital platforms, and a control group taught by traditional methods.

Participants and Selection Criteria

The study included 200 economics students selected based on their initial knowledge of ICT and prior experience using computers and the internet. The experimental group received specialized educational programs developed for this study, which:

utilized electronic resources to improve ICT-related skills,
included skills in database searching, data processing with analytical software,
and presentation of economic information.

Data were collected through pre-tests and surveys, aimed at assessing students' knowledge and skills in ICT. Differences between the control and experimental groups were then analyzed.

The gathered data were statistically analyzed using ANOVA and t-tests to assess differences between the groups. Identifying pedagogical opportunities for developing ICT competence can enrich economics curricula with innovative approaches, emphasizing the importance of ICT competence in training economics specialists.

Results and Discussion. Two hundred students participated in the study to evaluate the effectiveness of ICT tools in economics education. The results indicate:

Impact of ICT Tools: Economic analysis skills among students increased by

30%-35%. Students effectively used ICT tools, especially in statistical software and economic modeling.

Test Results: In the initial test, 45% of students could effectively use ICT tools, while in the final test, this percentage increased to 80%.

Statistical Analysis: Differences in ICT competence between students were clearly demonstrated in the data.

Table 1

Group	Initial Scores (%)	Final Scores (%)	Difference (%)
Group 1	47	78	+31
Group 2	50	80	+30
Group 3	45	82	+37
Group 4	48	79	+31

The study results highlight the effectiveness of ICT tools in improving students' skills in economic analysis and decision-making, with a 30%-35% increase in competence reflecting the benefits of integrating ICT into the educational process. Interactive and digital tools increased motivation among students and helped them assimilate economic concepts along with practical skills. The results of tests and surveys reveal a significant increase in ICT skills among students, confirming the vital role of ICT tools in enhancing skills for economic analysis and decision-making.

Conclusion.

This study examined the process of developing ICT competence in economics students and its impact on the effectiveness of education. The results indicate that ICT tools effectively improve skills in economic analysis and decision-making. Test results show an increase from 45% in the initial test to 80% in the final test.

Interactive learning tools and digital platforms increased motivation among students and improved their skills in information processing. Integrating ICT tools into educational programs helps develop practical skills among students, allowing for effective economic analysis. The results underscore the importance of developing

ICT competence for students and the need for broader integration into the educational process. Future research should focus on studying these approaches more deeply and improving educational programs.

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